

Strongly Binary G^* -Closed Set in Binary Topological Spaces

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published online: 22 July 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Name R. Premkumar</p> <p>KEYWORDS: binary closed, binary g^*-closed set and strongly binary g^*-closed set</p>	<p>In this paper, we introduce the concept of strongly binary g^*-closed sets in binary topological space and we investigate the group of structure of the set of all strongly binary g^*-closed sets.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

In 1970 Levine [7] gives the concept and properties of generalized closed (briefly g -closed) sets and the complement of g -closed set is said to be g -open set. Njasted [16] introduced and studied the concept of α -sets. Later these sets are called as α -open sets in 1983. Mashhours et.al [10] introduced and studied the concept of α -closed sets, α -closure of set, α -continuous functions, α -open functions and α -closed functions in topological spaces. Maki et.al [8, 9] introduced and studied generalized α -closed sets and α -generalized closed sets. In 2011, S.Nithyanantha Jothi and P.Thangavelu [11] introduced topology between two sets and also studied some of their properties. Topology between two sets is the binary structure from X to Y which is defined to be the ordered pairs (A, B) where $A \subseteq X$ and $B \subseteq Y$. In this paper, we introduce the concept of strongly binary g^* -closed sets in binary topological space and we investigate the group of structure of the set of all strongly binary g^* -closed sets.

Throughout this paper, (X, Y) denote binary topological spaces (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) .

Let X and Y be any two nonempty sets. A binary topology [11] from X to Y is a binary structure $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(X) \times \mathcal{P}(Y)$ that satisfies the axioms namely

1. (\emptyset, \emptyset) and $(X, Y) \in \mathcal{M}$,

2. $(A_1 \cap A_2, B_1 \cap B_2) \in \mathcal{M}$ whenever $(A_1, B_1) \in \mathcal{M}$ and $(A_2, B_2) \in \mathcal{M}$, and 3. If $\{(A_\alpha, B_\alpha) : \alpha \in \delta\}$ is a family of members of \mathcal{M} , then $(\bigcup_{\alpha \in \delta} A_\alpha, \bigcup_{\alpha \in \delta} B_\alpha) \in \mathcal{M}$.

If \mathcal{M} is a binary topology from X to Y then the triplet (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary topological space and the members of \mathcal{M} are called the binary open subsets of the binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . The elements of $X \times Y$ are called the binary points of the binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . If $Y = X$ then \mathcal{M} is called a binary topology on X in which case we write (X, \mathcal{M}) as a binary topological space.

Definition 1.1 [11] Let X and Y be any two nonempty sets and let (A, B) and $(C, D) \in \mathcal{P}(X) \times \mathcal{P}(Y)$. We say that $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D)$ if $A \subseteq C$ and $B \subseteq D$.

Definition 1.2 [11] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $A \subseteq X, B \subseteq Y$. Then (A, B) is called binary closed in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) if $(X \setminus A, Y \setminus B) \in \mathcal{M}$.

Proposition 1.3 [11] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Let $(A, B)^{1*} = \bigcap \{A_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary closed and } (A, B) \subseteq (A_\alpha, B_\alpha)\}$ and $(A, B)^{2*} = \bigcap \{B_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary closed and } (A, B) \subseteq (A_\alpha, B_\alpha)\}$. Then $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is binary closed and $(A, B) \subseteq ((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$.

Proposition 1.4 [11] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Let $(A, B)^{1*} = \bigcup \{A_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary open and } (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \subseteq (A, B)\}$ and

$(A, B)^{2*} = \cup \{B_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary open and } (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \subseteq (A, B)\}$.

Definition 1.5 [11] The ordered pair $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is called the binary closure of (A, B) , denoted by $b-cl(A, B)$ in the binary space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) where $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$.

Definition 1.6 [11] The ordered pair $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ defined in proposition 1.4 is called the binary interior of (A, B) , denoted by $b-int(A, B)$. Here $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is binary open and $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*}) \subseteq (A, B)$.

Definition 1.7 [11] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and let $(x, y) \subseteq (X, Y)$. The binary open set (A, B) is said to be a binary neighbourhood of (x, y) if $x \in A$ and $y \in B$.

Proposition 1.8 [11] Let $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D) \subseteq (X, Y)$ and (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space. Then, the following statements hold:

1. $b-int(A, B) \subseteq (A, B)$.
2. If (A, B) is binary open, then $b-int(A, B) = (A, B)$.
3. $b-int(A, B) \subseteq b-int(C, D)$.
4. $b-int(b-int(A, B)) = b-int(A, B)$.
5. $(A, B) \subseteq b-cl(A, B)$.
6. If (A, B) is binary closed, then $b-cl(A, B) = (A, B)$.
7. $b-cl(A, B) \subseteq b-cl(C, D)$.
8. $b-cl(b-cl(A, B)) = b-cl(A, B)$.

Definition 1.9 A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called

1. a binary semi open set [15] if $(A, B) \subseteq b-cl(b-int(A, B))$.
2. a binary pre open set [5] if $(A, B) \subseteq b-int(b-cl(A, B))$,
3. a binary regular open set [14] if $(A, B) = b-int(b-cl(A, B))$.

Definition 1.10 A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called

1. a binary g -closed set [12] if $b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.
2. a binary gs -closed set [17] if $b-scl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.
3. a binary sg -closed set [17] if $b-scl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary semi open.
4. a binary gr -closed set [14] if $b-rcl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.
5. a binary gsp -closed set [6] if $b-\beta cl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.

Definition 1.11 [4] Let (A, B) be a subset of a binary topological space (X, Y) . Then (A, B) is called a binary g^* -closed set if $b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (P, Q)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (P, Q)$ and (P, Q) is binary g -open in (X, Y) .

Definition 1.12 [2] A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary α -open if $(A, B) \subseteq b-int(b-cl(b-int(A, B)))$.

Definition 1.13 [1] A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary αg -closed if $b-\alpha cl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.

II. STRONGLY BINARY G^* -CLOSED SETS

Definition 2.1 Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and (A, B) be its subset, then (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed set if $b-cl(b-int(A, B)) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary g -open.

Theorem 2.2 Every binary closed set is strongly binary g^* -closed but not conversely.

Proof. The proof is immediate from the definition of binary closed set.

Example 2.3 Let $X = \{1, 2\}$, $Y = \{a, b\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{a\}), (\{1\}, \phi), (\{1\}, \{a\}), (\{1\}, \{b\}), (\{1\}, Y), (\{2\}, \{a\}), (X, \{a\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then the set $(\{1\}, \{a\})$ is strongly binary g^* -closed set but not a binary closed in (X, Y) .

Theorem 2.4 If a subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is binary g^* -closed then it is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) but not conversely.

Proof. Suppose (A, B) is binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) . Let (G, H) be an binary open set containing (A, B) in (X, Y) . Then (G, H) contains $b-cl(A, B)$. Now $(G, H) \supseteq b-cl(A, B) \supseteq b-cl(b-int(A, B))$. Thus (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) .

Example 2.5 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (\{a, b\}, \{1\}), (\{a, b\}, Y), (X, Y)\}$. Then the set $(\{a\}, \{2\})$ is strongly binary g^* -closed but not binary g^* -closed set.

Theorem 2.6 If (A, B) is subset of a binary topological space (X, Y) is binary open and strongly binary g^* -closed then it is binary closed.

Proof. Suppose a subset (A, B) of (X, Y) is both binary open and strongly binary g^* -closed. Now $(A, B) \supseteq b-cl(b-int(A, B)) \supseteq b-cl(A, B)$. Therefore $(A, B) \supseteq b-cl(A, B)$. Since $b-cl(A, B) \supseteq (A, B)$. We have $(A, B) \supseteq b-cl(A, B)$. Thus (A, B) is binary closed in (X, Y) .

Corollary 2.7 If (A, B) is both binary open and strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) then it is both binary regular open and binary regular closed in (X, Y) .

Proof. As (A, B) is binary open $(A, B) = b-int(A, B) = b-int(b-cl(A, B))$, since (A, B) is binary closed. Thus (A, B) is binary regular open. Again (A, B) is binary open in (X, Y) , $b-$

$\text{cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) = \text{b-cl}(A, B)$. As (A, B) is binary closed $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) = (A, B)$. Thus (A, B) is binary regular closed.

Corollary 2.8 If (A, B) is both binary open and strongly binary g^* -closed then it is binary rg -closed.

Theorem 2.9 If a subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y) is both strongly binary g^* -closed and binary semi open then it is binary g^* -closed.

Proof. Suppose (A, B) is both strongly binary g^* -closed and binary semi open in (X, Y) . Let (G, H) be an binary open set containing (A, B) . As (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed, $(G, H) \supseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$. Now $(G, H) \supseteq \text{b-cl}(A, B)$. Since (A, B) is binary semi open. Thus (A, B) is binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) .

Corollary 2.10 If a subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y) is both strongly binary g^* -closed and binary open then it is binary g^* -closed set.

Proof. As every binary open set is binary semi open by the above theorem the proof follows.

Theorem 2.11 A set (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed iff $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ contains no non empty binary closed set.

Proof. **Necessary part:** Suppose that (E, F) is non empty binary closed subset of $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$. Now $(E, F) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ implies $(E, F) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \cap (A, B)^c$, since $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B) = \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \cap (A, B)^c$. Thus $(E, F) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$. Now $(E, F) \subseteq (A, B)^c$ implies $(A, B) \subseteq (A, B)^c$. Here $(E, F)^c$ is binary g -open and (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed, we have $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \subseteq (E, F)^c$. Thus $(E, F) \subseteq (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)))^c$. Hence $(E, F) \subseteq (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))) \cap (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)))^c = (\phi, \phi)$. Therefore $(E, F) = (\phi, \phi) \Rightarrow \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ contains no non empty binary closed sets.

Sufficient part: Let $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$, (G, H) is binary g -open. Suppose that $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$ is not contained in (G, H) then $(\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)))^c$ is a non empty binary closed set $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ which is a contradiction. Therefore $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \subseteq (G, H)$ and hence (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed.

Corollary 2.12 A strongly binary g^* -closed set (A, B) is binary regular closed iff $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \supseteq (A, B)$.

Proof. Assume that (A, B) is binary regular closed. Since $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) = (A, B)$, $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$ is binary regular closed and hence binary closed.

Conversely assume that $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ is binary closed. By above theorem $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ contains no non empty binary closed set. Therefore $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$. Thus (A, B) is binary regular closed.

Theorem 2.13 Suppose that $(C, D) \subseteq (A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$, (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed set relative to (A, B) and that both binary open and strongly binary g^* -closed subset of (X, Y) then (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed set relative to (X, Y) .

Proof. Let $(C, D) \subseteq (G, H)$ and (G, H) be an binary open set in (X, Y) . But given that $(C, D) \subseteq (A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$, therefore $(C, D) \subseteq (A, B)$ and $(C, D) \subseteq (G, H)$. This implies $(C, D) \subseteq (A, B) \cap (G, H)$. Since (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed relative to (A, B) ,

$$\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq (A, B) \cap (G, H).$$

(ie) $(A, B) \cap \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq (A, B) \cap (G, H)$. This implies $(A, B) \cap \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq (G, H)$. Thus

$$((A, B) \cap (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c \subseteq (G, H) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c$$

implies $(A, B) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c \subseteq (G, H) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c$. Since (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) , we have $(\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))) \subseteq (G, H) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c$. Also $(C, D) \subseteq (A, B) \Rightarrow \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$. Thus $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) \subseteq (G, H) \cup (\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)))^c$. Therefore (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed set relative to (X, Y) .

Corollary 2.14 Let (A, B) be strongly binary g^* -closed and suppose that (E, F) is binary closed then $(A, B) \cap (E, F)$ is strongly binary g^* -closed set.

Proof. To show that $(A, B) \cap (E, F)$ is strongly binary g^* -closed, we have to show $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B) \cap (E, F)) \subseteq (G, H)$ whenever $(A, B) \cap (E, F) \subseteq (G, H)$ and (G, H) is binary g -open. $(A, B) \cap (E, F)$ is binary closed in (A, B) and so strongly binary g^* -closed in (C, D) . By the above theorem $(A, B) \cap (E, F)$ is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) . Since $(A, B) \cap (E, F) \subseteq (A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$.

Theorem 2.15 If (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed and $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$ then (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed.

Proof. Given that $(C, D) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$ then $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B))$,

$$\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) - (C, D) \subseteq \text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B).$$

Since $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D)$. As (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed by the above theorem $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ contains no non empty binary closed set, $\text{b-cl}(\text{b-int}(C, D)) - (C, D)$

contains no empty binary closed set. Again by theorem 2.13, (C, D) is strongly binary g^* -closed set.

Theorem 2.16 Let $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V) \subseteq (X, Y)$ and suppose that (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) then (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed relative to (U, V) .

Proof. Given that $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V) \subseteq (X, Y)$ and (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) . To show that (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed relative to (U, V) , let $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V) \cap (G, H)$, where (G, H) is binary g -open in (X, Y) . Since (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed in (X, Y) , $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$ implies $b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B)) \subseteq (G, H)$.

(ie) $(U, V) \cap b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B)) \subseteq (U, V) \cap (G, H)$, where $(U, V) \cap b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B))$ is binary closure of binary interior of (A, B) in (U, V) . Thus (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed relative to (U, V) .

Theorem 2.17 If a subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y) is binary gsp -closed then it is strongly binary g^* -closed.

Proof. Suppose that (A, B) is binary gsp -closed in (X, Y) , let (G, H) be binary open set containing (A, B) . Then $(G, H) \subseteq bsp\text{-cl}(A, B)$, $(A, B) \cup (G, H) \supseteq (A, B) \cup (b\text{-int}(b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B))))$ which implies $(G, H) \supseteq b\text{-int}(b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B)))$ as (G, H) is binary open. (ie) $(G, H) \supseteq b\text{-cl}(b\text{-int}(A, B)) - (A, B)$ is strongly binary g^* -closed set in (X, Y) .

Theorem 2.18 Every strongly binary g^* -closed set is an binary αg -closed set and hence binary gs -closed but not conversely.

Proof. Let (A, B) be a strongly binary g^* -closed set of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . By above theorem, (A, B) is binary g -closed and binary αg -closed. Then we know that every binary g -closed set is binary gs -closed. By above theorem every strongly binary g^* -closed set is binary gs -closed.

Example 2.19 Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{a\}, Y), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then the set $(\{a\}, \phi)$ is strongly binary g^* -closed set but not binary αg -closed.

Example 2.20 Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{1\}), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \{1\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then the set (ϕ, Y) is strongly binary g^* -closed set but not binary gs -closed.

III. MORE ON STRONGLY BINARY G^* -OPEN SETS

Definition 3.1 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space and $(x, y) \in (X, Y)$. A subset (J, K) of (X, Y) is said to be strongly binary g^* -neighbourhood of (x, y) if there exists an strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) such that $(x, y) \in (G, H) \subset (J, K)$.

The collection of all strongly binary g^* -neighborhoods of $(x, y) \in (J, K)$ is called a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood system at (x, y) and shall be denoted by strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$.

Definition 3.2 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space and (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y) . (A, B) subset (J, K) of (X, Y) is said to be strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (A, B) if there exists a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) such that $(A, B) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$.

Definition 3.3 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space and (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y) . A point $(x, y) \in (A, B)$ is said to be a strongly binary g^* -interior point of (A, B) , if (A, B) is strongly binary $g^*N(x, y)$. The set of all strongly binary g^* -interior points of (A, B) is called a strongly binary g^* -interior points of (A, B) and is denoted by $SBG^*INT(A, B)$. $SBG^*INT(A, B) = \cup \{(G, H): (G, H) \text{ is strongly binary } g^* \text{-open, } (G, H) \subset (A, B)\}$.

Definition 3.4 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space and (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y) . A point $(x, y) \in (A, B)$ is said to be a strongly binary g^* -closure of (A, B) . Then $SBG^*CL(A, B) = \cap \{(E, F): (A, B) \subset (E, F) \text{ in strongly binary } g^* \text{-closed } BG^*C(X, Y, \mathcal{M})\}$.

Theorem 3.5 A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space is strongly binary g^* -open if it is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of each points.

Proof. Let (G, H) be subset of a binary topological space be strongly binary g^* -open. Then for every $(x, y) \in (X, Y)$, $(x, y) \in (G, H) \subseteq (G, H)$, and therefore (G, H) is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of each of the points.

Theorem 3.6 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space. If (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed subset of (X, Y) and $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$ if and only if for any strongly binary g^* -neighborhood (J, K) of (x, y) in (X, Y) , $(J, K) \cap (A, B) \neq (\phi, \phi)$.

Proof. Let us assume that there is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood (J, K) of the point (x, y) in (X, Y) such that $(J, K) \cap (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$. There exists a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) of (X, Y) such that $(x, y) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$. Therefore we have $(G, H) \cap (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$ and so $(x, y) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$.

Then $SBG^*CL(A, B) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$ and therefore $(x, y) \notin SBG^*CL(A, B)$, which contradicts the hypothesis that $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$.

Therefore $(J, K) \cap (A, B) \neq (\phi, \phi)$.

Conversely, suppose that $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$. Then there exists a strongly binary g^* -closed set (G, H) of (X, Y)

such that $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$ and $(x, y) \notin (G, H)$. Thus $(x, y) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$ and $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is strongly binary g^* -open in (X, Y) and hence $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is strongly binary g^* -open in (X, Y) and hence $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (x, y) in (X, Y) . But $(A, B) \cap ((X, Y) - (G, H)) = (\phi, \phi)$ which is a contradiction. Hence $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$.

Theorem 3.7 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space and $(x, y) \in (X, Y)$. Let strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$ be a collection of all strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (x, y) . Then

1. Strongly $bg^*N(x, y) \neq (\phi, \phi)$ and (x, y) belongs to each member of Strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$.
2. The intersection of the any two members of strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$ is again a member of strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$.
3. If $(J, K) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$ and $(U, V) \subseteq (J, K)$, then $(U, V) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$.
4. Each member $(J, K) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$ is a superset of a member $(G, H) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(x, y)$ where (G, H) is a strongly binary g^* -open set.

Proof. 1. Since (X, Y) is strongly binary g^* -open set containing (p, q) , it is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of every $(p, q) \in (X, Y)$. Hence there exist at least one strongly binary g^* -neighborhood namely (X, Y) for each $(p, q) \in (X, Y)$ there is strongly $bg^*N(p, q) \neq (\phi, \phi)$. Let $(J, K) \in$ strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$, (J, K) is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (p, q) , then there exists a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) such that $(p, q) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$, so $(p, q) \in (J, K)$. therefore (p, q) belongs to every number (J, K) strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$.

2. Let $(J, K) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$ and $(U, V) \in$ strongly binary $g^*N(p, q)$. There exists strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) and (E, F) such that $(p, q) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$ and $(p, q) \in (E, F) \subseteq (U, V)$.

Hence $(p, q) \in (G, H) \cap (E, F) \subseteq (U, V) \cap (J, K)$. Note that $(G, H) \cap (E, F)$ is a strongly binary g^* -open set. Therefore it follows that $(J, K) \cap (U, V)$ is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (p, q) . Hence $(J, K) \cap (U, V) \in$ strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$.

3. If $(J, K) \in$ strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$ then there is a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) such that $(p, q) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$. Since $(U, V) \subseteq (J, K)$, (U, V) is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (p, q) . Hence $(U, V) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$.

4. Let $(J, K) \in$ strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$ then there exists a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) , such that $(p, q) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$. Since (G, H) is strongly binary g^* -open set and $(p, q) \in (G, H)$, (G, H) is strongly binary g^* -

neighborhood of (p, q) . Therefore $(G, H) \in$ Strongly $bg^*N(p, q)$ and also $(G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$.

Theorem 3.8 Let (X, Y) be a binary topological space. If (A, B) is strongly binary g^* -closed subset of (X, Y) and $(x, y) \in SBG^*INT(A, B)$ if and only if for any strongly binary g^* -neighborhood (J, K) of (x, y) in (X, Y) , $(J, K) \cap (A, B) \neq (\phi, \phi)$.

Proof. Let us assume that there is strongly binary g^* -neighborhood (J, K) of the point (x, y) in (X, Y) such that $(J, K) \cap (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$. There exists an strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) of (X, Y) such that $(x, y) \in (G, H) \subseteq (J, K)$. Therefore we have $(G, H) \cap (A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$ and so $(x, y) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$.

Then $SBG^*CL(A, B) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$ and therefore $(x, y) \notin SBG^*CL(A, B)$, which is a contradiction to the hypothesis that $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$. Therefore $(J, K) \cap (A, B) \neq (\phi, \phi)$.

Conversely, suppose that $(x, y) \notin SBG^*CL(A, B)$, then there exists a strongly binary g^* -closed set (G, H) of (X, Y) such that $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$ and $(x, y) \notin (G, H)$. Thus $(x, y) \in (X, Y) - (G, H)$ and $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is strongly binary g^* -open in (X, Y) and hence $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is a strongly binary g^* -neighborhood of (x, y) in (X, Y) . But $(A, B) \cap ((X, Y) - (G, H)) = (\phi, \phi)$ which is a contradiction. Hence $(x, y) \in SBG^*CL(A, B)$.

Proposition 3.9 If (A, B) is a subset of (X, Y) , then $SBG^*INT(A, B) = \cup \{(G, H): (G, H) \text{ is strongly binary } g^*\text{-open, } (G, H) \subset (A, B)\}$.

Proof. Let (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y) , $(x, y) \in SBG^*INT(A, B) \Leftrightarrow (x, y)$ is a strongly binary g^* -interior point of (A, B) , (A, B) is a strongly binary $g^*N(x, y)$ which implies that there exists a strongly binary g^* -open set (G, H) such that $(x, y) \in (G, H) \subset (A, B)$, $(x, y) \in \cup \{(G, H): (G, H) \text{ is strongly binary } g^*\text{-open, } (G, H) \subset (A, B)\}$.

Hence $SBG^*INT(A, B) = \cup \{(G, H): (G, H) \text{ is strongly binary } g^*\text{-open, } (G, H) \subset (A, B)\}$.

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